

**Deliverable D-JRP-
PARADISE-WP3.5
Report of inter-laboratory
comparison of MLST
schemes for *C. parvum* and
*G. duodenalis***

**Workpackage 3 of
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D-JRP-PARADISE-WP3.5

REPORT OF INTERLABORATORY COMPARISON OF MLST SCHEMES FOR *C. PARVUM* AND *G. DUODENALIS*

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JRP19-ET1.1-PARADISE – PARAsite Detection, ISolation and Evaluation**

(<https://onehealthejp.eu/jrp-paradise/>)

Work Package:

JRP- PARADISE–WP3 Design, implementation and validation of MLST schemes

Task:

JRP-PARADISE-PARADISE-WP3-T3 Inter-laboratory comparison of MLST schemes

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1. Background

The PARADISE project aims to deliver informative typing schemes and innovative detection strategies applicable to food matrices for the food-borne parasites *Cryptosporidium* and *Giardia*. Using genomics and metagenomics, the project is generating much needed data to enrich our understanding of the epidemiology and genomics of these organisms, and provide the basis for development and testing of improved strain-typing schemes. In parallel, strategies (nanobodies, aptamers, use of hybridization probes) to enrich for the target pathogens in different matrices are under development and validation. These new methodologies will form the basis for integrated approaches to control *Cryptosporidium* and *Giardia* in the European food chain.

The objectives of PARADISE WP3 are:

- To select new markers *in silico* for robust high resolution genotyping of *C. parvum* and *Giardia duodenalis* using whole genome data generated in WP2-T1, unpublished data from within the consortium and publicly available data
- To develop multilocus sequence typing (MLST) schemes for *C. parvum* and *G. duodenalis*

- To conduct an inter-laboratory comparison of MLST schemes

This deliverable, D-JRP-PARADISE-WP3.5, reports on the work carried out to address the third objective of PARADISE WP3, namely an interlaboratory testing of the MLST developed in W3P-1 (Deliverable D-JRP-PARADISE-WP3.1 Report on the *in silico* selection of highly polymorphic sequences in *C. parvum* and *G. duodenalis* genomes; <https://zenodo.org/record/4452772>) and WP3-2 (Deliverable D-JRP-PARADISE-WP3.2 Report on the identification of markers for multi-locus sequence typing of *Cryptosporidium parvum* and *Giardia duodenalis*; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5494475>).

2. Organization of the ring tests

Beginning of February 2022, a total of 14 laboratories from 11 European countries were invited to participate at the ring tests (RT). The SOPs for both *C. parvum* and *G. duodenalis* MLSTs were provided and participants were instructed to buy the necessary reagents and obtain access to specific sequence analysis programs. Two separate virtual trainings were conducted by RKI (for *G. duodenalis*) and ISS (for *C. parvum*) in April/May 2022 to illustrate the specific aims and sequence analysis workflow prior to the shipment of the RT samples. The RT samples included five *G. duodenalis* DNAs, which were tested and provided by RKI, and five *C. parvum* DNAs, which were tested and provided by SVA/ISS, and re-tested by BfR prior to dispatch to all laboratories in May 2022. In addition to reporting the MLST (*C. parvum*) and the consensus sequences with ASH indicated (*Giardia*) of each sample the participants were instructed to contribute the raw sequence data by uploading files into the project cloud space. The results were to be reported in the provided results sheets 4-6 weeks after dispatch.

3. *Cryptosporidium parvum*

Each participant was asked to sequence the PCR products from the eight markers comprised in the MLST scheme, obtained using the five DNAs provided. Next, they were asked to compare the consensus sequences obtained for each DNA and each marker with the previously identified reference sequences (alleles), which were provided as text files. Finally, participants were asked to assign alleles to each sample for each marker, and to return the results to ISS. It was suggested to add comments on eventual technical challenges (e.g., quality of the Sanger sequencing reaction, presence of mixed positions in the electropherograms) encountered during the RT.

3.1 Results

The results of the RT are presented in Appendix 1. One partner (number 4) was not able to conduct the RT and did not return results; therefore, data from 13 laboratories were available. Analyses showed a good overall

congruency in the assignment of the alleles made by the participants. Indeed, out of a total of 520 allele assignment, 28 (5%) were not in line with the expected result. These discrepancies were largely attributable to insufficient quality or length of the sequencing reaction, which prevented a precise assignment at the level of alleles. This problem was reported in particular by partner 8 and 9 (see Appendix 1). Of note, sample 3 was from a mixed infection and one double peak was expected at marker CP0024650. However, the presence of the double peak, which should lead to the identification of both allele 1 and allele 3, was reported by 5 partners, whereas the others reported allele 1 only. This was due to the subjective evaluation of sequencing electropherograms by individual participants.

3.2 Conclusion

The RT confirmed that the SOP was correctly implemented and used by the participating laboratories. The limited percentage of failure in the assignment of sequences to the level of alleles was largely due to a low quality of Sanger sequencing reactions obtained by some partners.

4. *Giardia duodenalis*

Each participant was asked to amplify and sequence the seven markers comprised in the MLST scheme, using the five DNAs provided. Next, they were asked to generate consensus sequences obtained for each DNA, including calling of respective allelic sequence heterogenic (ASH) positions, according to the provided protocol and as presented in the online training. Participants were asked to return the consensus sequences of each marker to the RKI together with the raw sequencing files. The RKI generated a second batch of consensus sequences from the raw sequences provided by the partners. The aim was to test whether PCR and sequencing in different labs would result in reproducible consensus sequences including respective ASH position. In two of the samples (sample 1 and 3) no ASH positions were present and in remaining 3 samples a various degree of ASH depending on marker and sample were present.

4.1 Results

The results of the RT are presented in Appendix 2. One partner (number 4) was not able to conduct the RT and did not return results; therefore, data from 13 laboratories were available. We compared the consensus sequence of each marker provided by each partner to the 'reference' sequences generated by RKI. In addition, RKI generated a second batch of consensus sequences from the raw data provided by the partners. For evaluation, only complete consensus sequences were used. The test DNA included samples with various degree of ASH and as expected the samples with no ASH positions (sample 1 and 3) resulted in very good sequence identities of consensus sequences submitted by different partners. Of 134 evaluated consensus sequences of the two samples with no ASH (including all complete consensus sequences from all 7 markers of all partners), 108 were identical, leading to an overall congruency for these two samples of approximately 80%. If the consensus sequences were generated by RKI from the raw data provided by the partners, the congruency of sequences increased to approximately 95% (144 identical sequences of 151 evaluated), indicating that further training in sequence data analysis will impact inter-laboratory consistency in a highly beneficial manner. It should be noted that some partners highlighted their insufficient basic knowledge in this

respect. Additionally, the remaining failures to call sequences correctly were due to technical issues resulting in bad raw sequence quality, which hinders adequate analysis.

Expectedly, the analysis of the consensus sequences retrieved by partners from the remaining 3 samples with expected ASH positions showed a much lower level of congruency. Here, only 13% (27 out of 202 evaluated sequences) of the sequences were identical to the reference consensus. This value increased to 31% (67 of 218 evaluated sequences) when raw data were analysed by RKI, but still represented a low percentage of sequences that were identical to the reference. This is likely due to the technical challenges introduced by PCR and sequencing techniques used to generate the sequences including ASH.

ASH affects dramatically the calling and this needs a more realistic assessment. Estimating the degree of correct ASH calling based on mean number of incorrectly called bases to expected ASH sites within the whole dataset showed that between 92-86% of the sites were called correctly by the partners (sample 2, 92%; sample 4, 86%; sample 5, 90%). This number increased to approximately 96% correctly called bases (sample 2, 95.9%; sample 4, 96,3%; sample 5, 96.3%) when sequences were analysed by RKI. Therefore, even in samples with high ASH values the overall congruency of sequence similarities was strikingly high.

4.2 Conclusion

The RT confirmed that the SOP was correctly implemented and used by the participating laboratories. This implies that the retrieved marker sequences are adequate to implement the typing scheme. The limiting factors for correct sequence calling were two-fold. First, low quality of Sanger sequencing results obtained by some partners hampered the assignment of sequences. Second, technical circumstances of PCR and Sanger sequencing may result in slight inconsistencies in consensus sequences at ASH positions. This can partly be avoided by consensus training for correct interpretation of sequences and ASH calling.

Appendix 1. Results of the *C. parvum* RT. Numbers refer to the allele(s) identified at each marker. Incorrect or inconclusive assignments are marked in red. Notes added by the participants are also shown as footnotes, with matching colours.

Marker CP0039030					
Partner	Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3	Sample 4	Sample 5
1	2	1	1	1	1
2	2	1	1	1	1
3	2	1	1	1	1
4	no data reported				
5	2	1	1	1	1
6	2	1	1	1	1
7	2	1	1	1	1
8	*	1	1	1	1
9	2	1	1	6	1 or 6
10	2	1	1	1	1
11	2	1	1	1	Inconclusive
12	2	1	1	1	1
13	2	1	1	1	1
14	2	1	1	1	1
% of labs with correct calling	92% (12/13)	100% (13/13)	100% (13/13)	92% (12/13)	85% (11/13)
T to C at position 229					
*Poor R sequence					

Marker CP0028230					
Partner	Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3	Sample 4	Sample 5
1	4	4	4	1	4
2	4	4	4	1	4
3	4	4	4	1	4
4	no data reported				
5	4	4	4	1	4
6	4	4	4	1	4
7	4	4	4	1	4
8	4*	4	4	1*	4
9	4	4	4	1	4
10	4	4	4	1	4
11	4	4	4	1	4
12	4	4	4	1	4
13	4	4	4	1	4
14	4	4	4	1	4
% of labs with	100% (13/13)	100% (13/13)	100% (13/13)	100% (13/13)	100% (13/13)

correct calling				
	* Poor/short F sequence			* Poor/short F sequence
	Double peak at position 205 R			
	Double peak at position 200 (R)			

d

Marker CP0031960					
Partner	Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3	Sample 4	Sample 5
1	2	7	7	1	7
2	2	7	2	1	7
3	2	7	2 or 7	1	7
4	no data reported	no data reported	no data reported	no data reported	no data reported
5	2	7	7	1	7
6	2	7	7	1	7
7	2	7	7	1	7
8	2	7	7	1	7
9	1 or 2 or 4 or 5 or 7	7	7	1	3
10	2	7	double peak position 64	1	7
11	Inconclusive (2 or 5)	7	7	1	7
12	2	7	7	1	7
13	2	7	7	1	7
14	2	7	7	1	7
% of labs with correct calling	85% (11/13)	100% (13/13)	77% (10/13)	100% (13/13)	92% (12/13)
		A to G at pos 563	doubtful assignment to alleles		
			doubtful assignment to alleles		

Marker CP0021750					
Partner	Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3	Sample 4	Sample 5
1	2	2	2	2	13
2	2	2	2	2	13
3	2 or 3 or 2 or 13	2 or 13	2 or 13	2 or 13	2 or 13
4	no data reported	no data reported	no data reported	no data reported	no data reported
5	2	2	2	2	13
6	2	2	2	2	13
7	2	2	2	2	13
8	2 or 3 or 12	2	2*	2	13
9	2 or 16	2 or 6 or 15 or 16	2	2	13
10	no sequence available	no sequence available	2	2	13
11	2	2	2	2	13

12	2	2	2	2	13
13	2	2	2	2	13
14	2	2	2	2	13
% of labs with correct calling	69% (9 /13)	77% (10/12)	92% (12/13)	92% (12/13)	92% (12/13)
	2 positions with double peaks		* Poor R sequence		
	2 positions with double peaks				

Marker CP0024650					
Partner	Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3	Sample 4	Sample 5
1	1	1	1 or 3	1	2
2	1	1	1	1	2
3	1	1	1 or 3	1	2
4	no data reported	no data reported	no data reported	no data reported	no data reported
5	1	1	1	1	2
6	2	1	1	1	2
7	1	1*	1 and 3**	1	2
8	1*	1	1	1*	2*
9	1	1	1	1	2
10	1	1	1 and 3	1	2
11	1	1	1	1	2
12	1	1	1 and 3	1	2
13	1	1	1	1	2
14	1	1	3	1	2
% of labs with correct calling	92% (12/13)	100% (13/13)	38% (5/13)	100% (13/13)	100% (13/13)
	* Poor/short F sequence	*SNP at position 521	doubtful assignment to alleles	* Poor/short F sequence	* Poor/short F sequence
			**Mix of alleles 1 and 3		

Marker CP0012400					
Partner	Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3	Sample 4	Sample 5
1	2	4	4	1	2
2	2	4	4	1	2
3	2	4	4	1	2
4	no data reported				
5	2	4	4	1	2
6	2	4	4	1	2

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7	2	4	4	1	2
8	2	4	4*	1	2
9	1 or 2 or 3 or 5 or 6	4	4	1	1 or 2 or 5 or 6
10	2	4	4	2	2
11	2	4	4	1	2
12	2	4	4	1	2
13	2	4	4	1	2
14	2	4	4	1	2
% of labs with correct calling	92% (12/13)	100% (13/13)	100% (13/13)	100% (13/13)	92% (12/13)
			* Poor/short F sequence		

Marker CP0007000					
Partner	Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3	Sample 4	Sample 5
1	4	4	4	1	4
2	4	4	4	1	4
3	4	4	4	1	4
4	no data reported	no data reported	no data reported	no data reported	no data reported
5	4	4	4	1	4
6	4	4	4	1	4
7	4	4	4	1	4
8	4*	4	4	1*	4*
9	1 or 4	1 or 4	1 or 4	1 or 4	4
10	4	4	4	1	1
11	4	4	4	1	4
12	4	4	4	1	4
13	4	4	4	1	4
14	4	4	4	1	4
% of labs with correct calling	92% (12/13)	92% (12/13)	92% (12/13)	92% (12/13)	92% (12/13)
* Poor/short F sequence				* Poor/short F sequence	* Poor/short F sequence

Marker CP0001010					
Partner	Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3	Sample 4	Sample 5
1	1	6	1	1	1

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2	1	6	1	1	1
3	1	6	1	1	1
4	no data reported	no data reported	no data reported	no data reported	no data reported
5	1	6	1	1	1
6	1	6	1	1	1
7	1	6	1	1	1
8	1	6	1	1	1
9	1	1	1	1	1
10	1	6	1	1	1
11	1	6	1	1	1
12	1	6	1	1	1
13	1	6	1	1	1
14	1	6	1	1	1
% of labs with correct calling	100% (13/13)	92% (12/13)	100% (13/13)	100% (13/13)	100% (13/13)
		indel Position 546	indel Position 546		

Appendix 2. Results of the *G. duodenalis* RT, presented per marker and including the notes added by the participants (color code). Consensus sequences were generated by the partners, including calling of respective allelic sequence heterogeneous (ASH) positions according to the provided protocol and as presented in the online training. Additionally, consensus sequences were generated by the RKI. Determined ASH positions in expected consensus sequences are provided. The table illustrates the number of non-correct bases called in comparison to the reference consensus sequence determined by RKI (0 = identical sequence, including correct ASH calling). It is further illustrated the number (and percentage) of partner laboratories that retrieved the correct/identical sequence.

	Marker 2 (consensus generated by partner)					Marker 2 (consensus generated by RKI)				
	Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3	Sample 4	Sample 5	Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3	Sample 4	Sample 5
Determined ASH sites in consensus	0	2	0	6	8	0	2	0	6	8
Partner	Number of non-correct bases called									
1	0	0	2	3	5	0	0	0	2	1
2	0	1	0	2	6	0	0	0	0	0
3	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
4	no data	no data	no data	no data	no data	no data	no data	no data	no data	no data
5	0	1	0	1	8	0	0	0	0	0
6	0	2	0	0	7	0	0	0	0	0
7	2	6	7	6	9	5	0	14	0	4
8	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
9	5	2	0	6	8	0	0	0	0	0
10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11	0	6	2	4	3	0	0	0	0	0
12	no data	no data	no data	no data	no data	0	0	0	0	0
13	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
14	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
# of labs with correct calling* / # of labs providing complete sequence* (%)	8/9 (89%)	4/10 (40%)	8/10 (80%)	5/10 (50%)	3/10 (30%)	8/9 (89%)	11/11 (100%)	10/11 (91%)	10/11 (91%)	9/11 (82%)

*excluding RKI, which provided reference consensus

	Marker 7 (consensus generated by partner)					Marker 7 (consensus generated by RKI)				
	Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3	Sample 4	Sample 5	Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3	Sample 4	Sample 5
Determined ASH sites in consensus	0	9	0	6	13	0	9	0	6	13
Partner	Number of non-correct bases called									
1	2	1	0	1	7	0	2	0	1	5
2	0	6	1	3	11	0	0	0	0	4
3	4	2	0	1	11	0	1	0	0	10
4	no data	no data	no data	no data	no data	no data	no data	no data	no data	no data
5	0	6	0	5	7	0	2	0	0	2
6	1	7	0	2	19	0	0	0	1	4
7	0	26	0	3	13	0	2	0	0	1

8	0	1	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	3
9	0	9	0	6	13	0	0	0	0	3
10	0	1	0	0	3	0	1	1	0	3
11	3	10	9	12	5	1	2	0	0	5
12	no data	no data	no data	no data	no data	12	1	0	0	4
13	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
14	0	1	0	1	4	0	1	0	1	2
# of labs with correct calling* / # of labs providing complete sequence* (%)	6/9 (67%)	0/10 (0%)	8/10 (80%)	2/10 (20%)	0/10 (0%)	10/11 (91%)	4/12 (33%)	11/12 (92%)	9/12 (75%)	0/12 (0%)

*excluding RKI, which provided reference consensus

	Marker 8 (consensus generated by partner)					Marker 8 (consensus generated by RKI)				
	Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3	Sample 4	Sample 5	Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3	Sample 4	Sample 5
Determined ASH sites in consensus	0	15	0	13	16	0	15	0	13	16
Partner	Number of non-correct bases called									
1	0	12	4	4	5	0	6	0	13	11
2	0	14	0	13	15	0	7	0	6	5
3	0	4	0	5	7	0	0	0	3	5
4	no data	no data	no data	no data	no data	no data	no data	no data	no data	no data
5		12	0	13	12	1	4	0	3	4
6	0	8	0	11	7	0	6	0	13	3
7	0	21	0	66	14	0	3	0	0	5
8	15	7	0	4	5	0	0	0	1	0
9	0	15	0	13	16	0	7	0	1	8
10	0	5	0	5	6	0	6	0	1	10
11	38	45	53	44	43	5	7	0	3	8
12	no data	no data	no data	no data	no data	7	21	0	0	4
13	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
14	1	9	0	3	5	0	5	0	3	3
# of labs with correct calling* / # of labs providing complete sequence* (%)	7/9 (78%)	0/10 (0%)	9/11 (82%)	0/10 (0%)	0/11 (0%)	9/10 (90%)	2/10 (20%)	12/12 (100%)	1/10 (10%)	1/12 (8%)

*excluding RKI, which provided reference consensus

	Marker 10 (consensus generated by partner)					Marker 10 (consensus generated by RKI)				
	Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3	Sample 4	Sample 5	Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3	Sample 4	Sample 5
Determined ASH sites in consensus	0	13	0	14	21	0	13	0	14	21
Partner	Number of non-correct bases called									
1	0	5	1	5	4	0	8	0	2	6
2	0	12	0	13	8	0	3	0	3	7
3	0	2	1	4	3	0	1	0	1	2

4	no data	no data	no data	no data	no data		no data	no data	no data	no data	no data
5	0	9	3	6	19		0	2	0	1	2
6	0	6	0	7	8		0	6	0	5	5
7			0	11	21				0	6	2
8	0	6	0	5	5		0	7	0	2	5
9	0	13	0	14	22		0	8	0	4	4
10	0	3	0	1	1		0	4	0	1	3
11	0	5	0	1	7		0	1	0	1	4
12	no data	no data	no data	no data	no data		0	13	0	3	2
13	0	0	0	0	0		0	0	0	0	0
14	1	8	0	3	0		0	3	0	1	3
# of labs with correct calling* / # of labs providing complete sequence* (%)	9/10 (90%)	0/9 (0%)	8/11 (73%)	0/11 (0%)	1/10 (10%)		10/10 (100%)	0/10 (0%)	12/12 (100%)	0/12 (0%)	0/10 (0%)

*excluding RKI, which provided reference consensus

	Marker 11 (consensus generated by partner)						Marker 11 (consensus generated by RKI)				
	Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3	Sample 4	Sample 5		Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3	Sample 4	Sample 5
Determined ASH sites in consensus	0	11	0	7	9		0	11	0	7	9
Partner	Number of non-correct bases called										
1	0	2	0	3	3		0	3	0	1	6
2	0	6	0	7	6		0	3	0	3	0
3	0	0	0	9	0		0	0	0	9	1
4	no data	no data	no data	no data	no data		no data	no data	no data	no data	no data
5	3	6	0		7		0	1	0	5	1
6	0	7	0	4	0		0	3	0	4	0
7	0		0	9	23		0		0	7	1
8	0	1	0	2	0		0	0	0	1	0
9	0	11	0	7	10		0	1	0	4	0
10	0	0	0	2	0		0	0	0	4	0
11	40	9	55	38	19		0	9	0	4	1
12	no data	no data	no data	no data	no data		0	5	0	5	0
13	0	0	0	0	0		0	0	0	0	0
14	1	1	0	2	0		0	2	0	4	0
# of labs with correct calling* / # of labs providing complete sequence* (%)	8/9 (89%)	2/9 (22%)	8/9 (89%)	0/9 (0%)	5/9 (56%)		12/12 (100%)	3/10 (30%)	10/10 (100%)	0/11 (0%)	7/10 (70%)

*excluding RKI, which provided reference consensus

	Marker 14 (consensus generated by partner)						Marker 14 (consensus generated by RKI)				
	Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3	Sample 4	Sample 5		Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3	Sample 4	Sample 5
Determined ASH sites in consensus	0	12	0	0	8		0	12	0	0	9

Partner	Number of non-correct bases called										
	0	2	0	0	2		0	1	0	1	6
1	0	8	0	0	82		0	1	0	0	5
2	0	5	1	0	6		0	1	0	0	4
3	no data	no data	no data	no data	no data		no data	no data	no data	no data	no data
4	0	5	0	10	6		0	1	0	2	3
5	16	2	0	0	4		0	1	0	0	3
6	4	11	0	1	6		1	5	0	2	3
7	0		0	0	4		0		0	0	5
8							0	0	0	0	3
9	0	1	0	0	3		0	1	0	0	5
10				65				5		0	
11	no data	no data	no data	no data	no data		0	5	0	0	3
12	0	0	0	0	0		0	0	0	0	0
13	4	2	1	1	4		1	1	0	0	5
14	4	2	1	1	4		1	1	0	0	5
# of labs with correct calling* / # of labs providing complete sequence* (%)	5/8 (63%)	0/7 (0%)	5/8 (63%)	5/9 (56%)	0/8 (0%)		9/10 (90%)	1/9 (11%)	11/11 (100%)	9/12 (75%)	0/11 (0%)

*excluding RKI, which provided reference consensus

	Marker 20 (consensus generated by partner)						Marker 20 (consensus generated by RKI)				
	Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3	Sample 4	Sample 5		Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3	Sample 4	Sample 5
Determined ASH sites in consensus	0	16	0	4	13		0	16	0	4	13
Partner	Number of non-correct bases called										
1	0	6	0	1	6		1	2	0	5	4
2	1	14	0	4	14		1	7	0	4	3
3	0	9	0	2	4		0	8	0	2	3
4	no data	no data	no data	no data	no data		no data	no data	no data	no data	no data
5	1	13	0	3	9		1	4	0	1	1
6	0	5	0	2	9		0	5	0	2	4
7	0	14	0	4	12		0	6	0	2	9
8	0	6	0	1	3		0	18	0	2	4
9	0	16	0	4	13		0	7	0	3	2
10	0	3	0	3	10		0	2	0	3	10
11	0			13	25		0	20	3	4	12
12							0	3	0	1	9
13	0	0	0	0	0		0	0	0	0	0
14	0	10	0	3	4		0	9	0	4	3
# of labs with correct calling* / # of labs providing complete sequence* (%)	9/11 (82%)	0/9 (0%)	10/10 (100%)	0/11 (0%)	0/10 (0%)		9/12 (75%)	0/10 (0%)	11/11 (100%)	0/11 (0%)	0/11 (0%)

*excluding RKI, which provided reference consensus

Legend	poor/short sequence	wrong sequences	no sequence reported	very poor sequences or not reported
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